

Maximized $N!$ Product over i $n(e_i)!$ Under Approximations Used Carry No More Information The Sum over i $e_i p(i) = E$ and Sum over i $p(i)=1$

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Mathematically, one may maximize a function subject to constraints which are introduced using Lagrange multipliers. In such a case, the function to be maximized usually differs from the constraints. In the case of Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy, one traditionally starts with the microcanonical picture of N particles with a total energy E and argues that any energy distribution which keeps E intact has the same weight. One may write the traditional function $N!$ Product over i $n(e_i)!$, where $n(e_i)$ = the number of particles with energy e_i , as representing the number of unique states. If one maximizes this (or actually its \ln), then one should have $n(e_i)$ which creates the maximum number of macrostates in the microcanonical system.

The actual process, however, is to introduce drastic approximations. In particular, $N \rightarrow$ infinite and one only imposes Sum over i $n(e_i) e_i = E_{\text{total}}$ or Sum over i $p(i) e_i = E/N = E_{\text{ave}}$. These approximations allow one to solve the problem mathematically in a straightforward manner. The argument we make is that these approximations actually render the $\ln(\text{number of states})$ into a function which no longer contains any more information than the constraints Sum over i $e_i p(i) = E_{\text{ave}}$ and Sum over i $p(i)=1$. Thus, we argue that if one accepts these approximations as representing (or closely approximating) reality, then the meaning of $N!$ Product over i $n(e_i)!$, which is very clear in a finite N case and represents the number of macrostates, is now only a function about the two constraints for which one seeks a stable solution. In other words, one cannot interpret $N!$ Product over i $n(e_i)!$ ((1)) under one set of approximations and then use a different set to actually solve for $n(e_i)$ and still retain the interpretation of ((1)). The set of approximations used to calculate $p(i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ represent the reality of the problem so to speak (we argue) and entropy under these approximations mimics the energy constraint, i.e. Sum over i $p(i) \ln(p(i))$ with $\ln(p(i)) = -e_i/T$.

Microcanonical Distribution

Traditionally, a microcanonical distribution is one in which one has N particles with total energy E . One may impose a priori the scenario that any distribution of E over the N particles carries the same weight. We argue that this is already an approximation because it violates conservation of momentum if one wishes to have a total momentum of zero. As a result, one already senses that approximations are going to be part of this approach.

Accepting the above idea (used in textbooks), one may write a priori, the number of macrostates:

$$N! \text{ Product over } i \ n(e_i)! \quad \text{As long as: } \text{Sum over } i \ e_i n(e_i) = E \text{ and } \text{Sum over } i \ n(e_i) = N \quad ((2))$$

Here the factorial expression has a very clear interpretation as the number of distinct arrangements of different e_i particles. Particles with the same e_i are taken to be identical. The usual approach is then to take \ln of ((2)) and maximize it with respect to the constraints listed in ((2)). In such a scenario, the factorial in ((2)) is a distinct function from the two

constraints. The \ln of the factorial in ((2)) is proportional to entropy and has a physical meaning of the number of macrostates.

We argue, however, that in order to actually maximize ((2)) with respect to the constraints, approximations are introduced which actually render the \ln of the factorial function into a function which carries no more information than the two constraints. In other words, one has to consider the function to be maximized under the approximations which are applied when one actually solves the problem and not under the viewpoint which exists before the approximations are imposed. The viewpoint of a distinct number of arrangements is fine at the initial point, but the approximations taken to solve the problem are strong and, we argue, change the information left in this function.

Examination of the Assumptions Needed to Solve for the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) Distribution

The solution of the MB distribution is based on the assumption of a very large (infinite) N . Furthermore, only an average energy constraint is imposed:

$$\sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave} = E/N \text{ where } N p(i) = n(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

These, we argue, are drastic assumptions. Under such approximations one does not need to worry about a factorial expression and can simply argue that a solution for $p(i)$ which treats every energy distribution E among N particles is:

$$p(i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((4))$$

Here T is some constant with energy units and $p(i)p(j) = p(i+j)$ so that any distribution has the same unnormalized product probability, i.e. weight, if one uses unnormalized $p(i)$'s.

((4)) uses drastic approximations, but yields a simple solution.

We next show that this solution is equivalent to considering only information contained in the two constraints $\sum_i p(i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$.

Consider a function which mimics the energy constraint (because the first constraint is general):

$$\sum_i h(p(i)) p(i) \quad ((5))$$

One may note that there are multiple $\{ p(i) \}$ sets which satisfy the two constraints. One wishes to find an equilibrium set $\{ p(i) \}$ which means a stable set. This means that changing $p(i)$ to $p(i)+dp(i)$ does not change ((5)) from representing $-E_{ave}/T$, the key constraint which must be upheld under the approximations used to obtain the MB distribution. Then:

$$(p+dp) h(p+dp) = ph(p) + h(p) dp + dh/dp dp p + \text{higher order terms} \quad ((6))$$

Summing, the first term yields $-E_{ave}/T$, and the next two terms must be 0 or cancel.

If $h(p) = -e_i/T$ so that ((5)) yields $-E_{ave}/T$ then:

$$dh/dp = 1 \text{ or } h = \ln(p) \text{ so } p = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((6))$$

In other words, $h(p(i)) = p(i)$ representing a functional form of the average energy, when maximized (stabilized), represents no more information than that contained in the two constraints. This yields a solution consistent with one which weights each macrostate in the same, using the unnormalized weight $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

This then brings one back to the factorial expression $N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)!$ which appears to be very different from the two constraints. It certainly is if one does not introduce drastic approximations, but we argue that given the drastic nature of the approximations, the \ln of this factorial function reduces to the form ((5)) which has already been argued to represent a functional form of the energy constraint. Thus, under the actual approximations used to solve the problem, the \ln of the factorial function is:

$$\ln(N!) + \text{Sum over } i \text{ } n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) \quad ((7)) \text{ using Stirling's approximation}$$

If $n(e_i) = Np(i)$ then a possible solution allows one to map $\ln(n(e_i))$ to $-e_i/T p(i)$. This turns out to be what is actually done when solving for the MB distribution and so the \ln of the factorial function no longer carries more information than the two constraints.

As a result, when introducing the factorial function in the finite N case, it has a very clear interpretation of distinct arrangements, but after the approximations used to solve for the MB distribution are imposed, it is rendered into a function which mimics the energy constraint and upon maximizing carries no more information than what is in the energy and $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(i)=1$ constraints, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that entropy is often introduced as $-k \ln$ number of distinct states. This is a clear definition if one uses $N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)!$ to define the number of macrostates. The problem which arises, we argue, is that drastic approximations are imposed in order to solve for the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and this clear definition of distinct arrangements loses its meaning. In fact, the information contained in the expression of \ln (factorial expression) is no more than the information contained in the two constraints $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$ and $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(i) = 1$. In fact, \ln (factorial expression) yields terms of the form $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } \ln(p(i)) p(i)$ which mimics the form of the energy constraint if $\ln(p(i)) = -e_i/T$, which is the case when one finds the solution. Thus, the problem is reduced to consider a function form of the energy constraint $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(i) h(p(i))$ with $h(p(i)) = -e_i/T$ such that $p \rightarrow p+dp$ leaves the function stable by making use of the two constraints. The view of distinct arrangements seems to be completely gone under these drastic approximations, yet the solution $p(i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ follows from these approximations and we argue that one should consider a viewpoint based on the

approximations used, not on an a priori expression $N! / \prod_{i=1}^n (e_i)!$ before the approximations are imposed.